

SYSTEMATICAL WORK IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION ORGANISATIONS AND ITS INFLUENCE TO THE CHILDREN

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Abstract. *This article describes the systematically work with children of senior preschool age, during systematic work in a preschool institution and in the family, on the basis of the developed program and methodological material, acquire knowledge about organizational qualities and show them in various activities.*

Keywords: *pre-school, kindergarten, learning, education, children, creativity, ability, organizing, working, brain-storming.*

To eliminate the existing gap in the formation of organizational qualities in children aged 5-7 years in preschool institutions, where a formative experiment was conducted with educators and parents.

At the first training, educators and parents were introduced to the concepts of "organizational qualities", "organizational skills", "discipline", "independence", "initiative", "responsibility", as well as the criteria and indicators of their formation in children.

In the course of the training, the following were used: the "brainstorming" method, a diagram that presents the organizational qualities of the individual, pedagogical situations, a memo for educators and parents with the concepts of organizational qualities.

At the second training, the participants were introduced to such qualities as discipline, independence and their essence. To consolidate knowledge about organizational qualities, the "cluster" and "fan" methods were used, as well as pedagogical situations and a reminder of discipline and independence.

At the third training, the participants were introduced to such organizational qualities as responsibility, initiative, diligence and their essence. Consolidation of knowledge about these qualities was carried out by the problematic method and independent work of the training participants.

The formative experiment was conducted on the basis of the preschool institution "Leader" of the Yakkasaray district of Tashkent from October 2009 to April 2010. 30 children of senior preschool age, 2 teachers and 30 parents took part in it. There are 62 respondents in total.

When we were convinced that most of the children had mastered the rules well, learned to follow them independently and quickly, the teacher no longer gathered the children near him before class, but suggested that they immediately come to the tables.

When organizing joint labor, a variety of situations were created that put children in front of the need to see the possibility of their participation in it, to show organizational qualities.

In the process of organizing various types of activities, initially, a manifestation of an emotionally positive attitude to work was observed, later, with a manifestation of interest in completing tasks, a conscious manifestation of certain qualities was assessed.

Let us consider in more detail the process of formation of independence in older preschoolers.

Identification of the degree of independence of preschoolers was carried out in the classroom for productive activities - drawing, application, design. The children were given tasks that met the program requirements and did not present any particular difficulty for them. The manifestation of independence of children in the performance of their labor assignments was studied. In each of the tasks, an assessment was given of the degree of independence of children in terms of manifestations of activity, initiative, responsibility, and the degree of effort made. Subsequently, a final assessment of the degree of independence of each child was derived for all types of productive activities. According to the degree of independence, the children were divided into 4 groups:

I. Lack of independence: low interest in the task, sometimes its complete absence. Lack of initiative. Frequent distractions, inability to concentrate, act without the help of an adult. Indifference to performance. In the game - passivity, inability to establish relationships with partners.

II. Beginnings of independence: low interest in the task in normal conditions and increasing in non-standard conditions. The presence of aimless ineffective actions, inertia. Turning to an adult for help without using one's own abilities. Activity is relatively high at the beginning of activity, then quickly declines due to satiety. The result is achieved using chaotic unorganized samples. The quality of the assignment remains out of the attention of children.

III. Average level of independence: in most cases, high interest in the task, but pronounced instability of behavior. At the beginning of activity, there is high activity, but when faced with difficulties, the pace of work decreases, actions become less focused, sometimes they are repeated to no avail. Adult support, a little help, encouragement often lead to a significant increase in activity and initiative. Children adequately evaluate their work, but the desire to improve the result is weakly expressed. Under normal conditions, there is incontinence, impulsiveness, careless performance of the task, however, with the complication of the task, higher organization, initiative and independence are manifested. In this case, a clearly pronounced emotional attitude to one's activities and the results achieved, a responsible attitude to work, a desire not to retreat from difficulties, to overcome them on one's own, without turning to an adult for help, are observed. The instability of behavior, the situational nature of manifestations of independence are especially clearly manifested in a collective plot-role-playing game.

IV. High level of independence: careful acceptance of the task, concentration, active actions aimed at achieving results. Appeals to adults for help are rare and appear only after exhausting their own capabilities. Work is done without haste, fussiness. There is a steady mobilization of efforts; the difficulties encountered do not demobilize children, but, on the contrary, cause a desire to find ways and means to overcome them at all costs. Task execution time is usually used rationally. The work is done conscientiously and carefully. Emotional reactions testify to the ability to independently assess the quality of one's work, objectively correlate the result obtained with the required one. In the role-playing game, children act as initiators, consistently adhere to the chosen plot.

The educational work was aimed at the formation of independence among older preschoolers in playing, productive and labor activities. Each of them stimulated initiative, independence and responsibility, but the significance of different activities for the development of these qualities was different. In the game, the main emphasis was placed on the development of

initiative - the core component of independence. The main meaning of productive activity was the development of independence. In the formation of responsibility, the most important was labor activity. The most important condition for the development of independence was the collective nature of the organization of all types of activities. There were three main stages in the upbringing and educational work. At the first stage, the prerequisites for the formation of independence were laid, at the second stage, conditions were created for its implementation, at the third stage, the trend towards independent activity was consolidated.

When organizing a collective role-playing game, the main attention was paid to activating the ability of children to independently apply new knowledge in the game, as well as to educating the ability to plan an upcoming game, independently build a plot and distribute roles. The means of developing independence were equipping preschoolers with knowledge that went beyond their direct experience, and teaching how to organize relationships, resolve emerging contradictions, and so on.

When organizing productive activities in the classroom and the simplest forms of joint work, the educator tried to update the motives for achieving the goal, the social significance of the activities carried out, and personal experience of success.

In order to consolidate independent forms of behavior, to make them more stable, the achievements of the children were regularly noted by the educator.

In the final part of the formative experiment, special attention was paid to the pace and organization of activities, the quality of the work performed in the classroom and in the performance of labor assignments. The instructions of the educator contributed to the mobilization of the forces and skills of the children. The confidence that the children would do well with the task helped them to do a lot during the lesson (30-35 minutes).

In the experiment, much attention was paid to an individual approach to children, taking into account their previously developed level of independence. Children with a low level of activity and initiative were addressed to more encouraging words, encouraging statements. They also received a relatively large number of indirect instructions. The educator actualized the motive of prestige, achieved emotional anticipation of the results of activity. In relation to children showing unstable, variable activity, such stimulating effects were used as increased control over the quality of work performance, the achievement of a positive result. Particular emphasis was placed on the actualization of the achievement motive, the awareness of the social significance of the results of activities. The teacher emphasized the need to complete the work on their own without asking for help. High demands were placed on children who showed the highest level of independence when assessing the quality of work. The main motives were the motives of the social significance of the results of activities and the success experienced.

Throughout the experiment, the principle of mandatory inclusion of each child in meaningful collective activities - play, work, and study - was implemented. Conditions were created to stimulate his activity, initiative, responsibility.

In the course of the development of independence, the content of the relationship between children and adults changed: the number of direct instructions decreased, the adult already acted as a person who only set the general direction of the children's activities. Thus, relations changed in the direction of strengthening the activity and initiative of children, their increasing independence from adults. At the same time, the assessment of the educator contributed to the correct self-organization of the child and the formation of adequate self-esteem in him. The

specific nature of the interaction between an adult and a child was determined by the individual characteristics of children: the level of formation of their independence, emotional reactions to evaluation, encouragement, etc.

Generalized data on the degree of self-determination in older preschoolers before and after the experiment are shown in Table 2.

As can be seen from the table, as a result of experimental training, there have been certain shifts in the degree of independence of children. Thus, the lack of independence in children decreased by 16.6% (5 children), the beginnings of independence by 16.7% (5 children); the average level increased by 29.4% (3 children), and the high level - by 23.4% (7 children). The behavior of children became more organized, the ability to achieve the set goal developed, to independently bring the work to the end, the quality of the task increased. This indicates a significant change in the attitude of children to their activities: a stable motivation has formed, which is considered by many researchers as the most important sign of the emergence of independence in preschoolers.

Table 2

The level of independence of older preschoolers before and after the experiment

Series	Level of independence				Total
	Lack of independence	The beginnings of independence	Middle level	High level	
Stating 30 children	9 (29,9%)	8 (26,6%)	10 (33,3%)	3 (9,9%)	99,7%
Control 30 children	4 (13,3%)	3 (9,9%)	13 (43,2%)	10 (33,3%)	99,7%

After the completion of the formative experiment, we summarized the results of a survey of children of senior preschool age to identify their knowledge of organizational qualities and their manifestation in the family before and after the experiment.

The survey of children was carried out on the basis of the developed material and was conducted individually, all answers were recorded in the questionnaire.

An analysis of the results of a survey of 30 children of senior preschool age to identify their knowledge of organizational qualities before and after the experiment showed that children before the experiment had difficulty in choosing the right solution in certain situations, in explaining their answers to questions, their understanding of such organizational qualities as discipline, independence, responsibility, diligence, initiative.

The arithmetic mean analysis of the survey of children is presented in Table 3.

This analysis shows the following: before the experiment, on average, 7 (23.3%) children had knowledge of discipline and independence, after the experiment - 13 (42.4%) and 12 (39.6%); about responsibility before the experiment - 10 (33%), diligence - 9 (29.7%) children, after the experiment - 12 (39.6%) and 13 (42.4%) children; about initiative before the experiment - 4 (13.2%) children, after it - 8 (26.4%).

Table 3

Arithmetic mean analysis of a survey of children of senior preschool age to identify their knowledge of organizational qualities before and after experiment

Name character	Before experiment			After experiment		
	Correct answer	Uncorrect answer	No answer	Correct answer	Uncorrect answer	No answer
Discipline	7 (23,3%)	6 (19,8%)	6 (19,8%)	13 (42,4%)	4 (13,2%)	4 (13,2%)
Independency	7 (23,3%)	5 (16,5%)	7 (23,3%)	12 (39,6%)	4 (13,2%)	5 (16,5%)
Responsibility	10 (33%)	5 (16,5%)	7 (23,3%)	12 (39,6%)	4 (13,2%)	4 (13,2%)
Hard working	9 (29,7%)	8 (26,4%)	8 (26,4%)	13 (42,4%)	4 (13,2%)	5 (16,5%)
Initiativity	4 (13,2%)	8 (26,4%)	11 (36,3%)	8 (26,4%)	8 (26,4%)	6 (19,8%)
Total	37:5	32:5	39:5	58:5	24:5	24:5
Arithmetic mean	7 (23,3%)	6 (19,8%)	8 (26,4%)	11 (36,3%)	5 (16,5%)	5 (16,5%)

We see that after the experiment, the level of knowledge of children about organizational qualities has increased markedly, which is reflected in Table 4.

Table 4

Levels of knowledge about organizational qualities
children of senior preschool age

Levels	Before experiment	After experiment
I High	7 (23,3%)	11 (36,3%)
II Middle	6 (19,8%)	5 (16,5%)
III Lower	8 (26,4%)	5 (16,5%)

The results of the formative experiment showed that the level of knowledge of senior preschool children about organizational qualities, according to the criteria we have determined, has changed significantly: Level I - high - increased by 13%; II level - medium and III level - low - decreased by 3.3%.

In our opinion, this was facilitated by the following:

- understanding by teachers of the importance of phased, systematic work on the formation of knowledge about organizational qualities among older preschoolers and the creation of conditions for their manifestation;
- systematic gradual expansion of ideas about organizational qualities.

The results of the analysis of observations of children of senior preschool age in the family in terms of their manifestation of organizational qualities are reflected in table 5.

Table 5

Summary table of the results of observations of 30 children of the eldest
preschool age in the family by their manifestation of organizational qualities

Name charecter	Manifests constantly		Manifests sometimes		Never manifest	
	Before experiment	After experiment	Before experiment	After experiment	Before experiment	After experiment
Discipline	10 (33%)	13 (43,29%)	15 (49,95%)	13 (43,29%)	5 (16,65%)	3 (9,93%)

Independen cy	7 (23,37%)	9 (29,97%)	12 (39,96%)	14 (46,62%)	10 (33%)	6 (19,98%)
Responsibili ty	7 (23,37%)	10 (33%)	12 (39,96%)	13 (43,29%)	10 (33%)	6 (19,98%)
Initiativity	6 (19,98%)	9 (29,97%)	11 (36,63%)	14 (46,62%)	8 (26,64%)	6 (19,98%)
Hard working	7 (23,37%)	9 (29,97%)	13 (43,29%)	15 (49,95%)	9 (29,97%)	5 (16,65%)
Total	37	50	63	69	45	25
Arithmetic mean	7	10	12	13	9	5
%	24,5	33	42	45,5	31,5	16,75

The arithmetic mean analysis showed that before the experiment 10 (33%) children showed discipline constantly, and after the experiment - 13 (43.29%); independence - before the experiment - 7 (23.37%), after the experiment - 9 (29.97%) children; responsibility - before the experiment - 7 (23.37%), after the experiment - 10 (33%) children; initiative - before the experiment - 6 (19.98%), after the experiment - 9 (29.97%) children; diligence - before the experiment - 7 (23.37%), after the experiment - 9 (29.97%) children.

Based on the arithmetic mean data obtained, the children were conditionally divided into levels (Table 6).

The results of the arithmetic mean analysis of the results of observations of children in terms of their manifestation of organizational qualities in the family show that the high level increased by 8.5%, the average level - by 3.5%, and the low level - decreased by 14.75%.

Table 6

Levels of manifestation in children of older preschool age
organizational skills in the family

Levels	Before experiment	After experiment
I High	7 (24,5%)	10 (33%)
II Middle	12 (42%)	13 (45,5%)
III Lower	9 (31,5%)	5 (16,75%)

In our opinion, this contributed to:

- awareness by parents of the importance of the formation of organizational qualities in preschoolers;
- their possession of the methodology for the formation of organizational qualities in children;
- creation in the family of conditions for the manifestation of organizational qualities by children.

Below we present the levels of assimilation by older preschoolers of knowledge about organizational qualities and their manifestation in the preschool educational institution and the family (table 7).

Table 7

Levels of learning by children of senior preschool age of knowledge about organizational
qualities and their manifestation in the preschool educational institution and the family

	In preschool educational institution	In family

Levels	Before experiment	After experiment	Before experiment	After experiment
I high	7 (23,3%)	11 (36,3%)	7 (24,5%)	10 (33%)
II middle	6 (19,8%)	5 (16,5%)	12 (42%)	13 (45,5%)
III lower	8 (26,4%)	5 (16,5%)	9 (31,5%)	5 (16,75%)

We see that the high level of learning about organizational qualities by children of senior preschool age and their manifestation in a preschool institution after the experiment increased by 13%, in the family - by 8.5%; the average level in a preschool institution decreased by 3.3%, in the family it increased by 3.5%; the low level in a preschool institution decreased by 9.9%, in the family - by 14.5%.

Based on the foregoing, it can be concluded that children of senior preschool age, with systematic work in a preschool institution and in the family, on the basis of the developed program and methodological material, acquire knowledge about organizational qualities and manifest them in various activities.

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